

ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH PLATES WITH INSERTS USING A HIGHER-ORDER SANDWICH PLATE THEORY

O. T. Thomsen and W. Rits

European Space Agency, European Space Technology and Research Centre,
Mechanical Systems Department, Structures and Mechanisms Division,
P. O. Box 299, NL-2200 AG Noordwijk, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

A "higher-order" sandwich plate theory is introduced for studying the mechanical response of sandwich plates with "through-the-thickness" inserts. The theory includes separate descriptions of face-plates and core, inclusion of different "potting" and "honeycomb" properties and general load specification. The theory is formulated as a set of first order partial differential equations, which is solved numerically using the "multi-segment method" of integration. It is demonstrated that parameters such as face stiffness, potting stiffness and potting geometry exerts significant influence on the elastic response. The study is concluded by a brief discussion of design aspects.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels with cores made of polymeric foam or honeycomb are susceptible to premature failure when the ideal load-transfer mechanism is disturbed. Such disturbances occur where external loads are introduced or where geometrical discontinuities are encountered. This is due to the fact, that the transverse flexibility affects the overall behaviour by reducing the "collaboration" between the faces-plates such that each face resists overall bending through local bending, in addition to the couple formed by the in-plane forces in the two face-plates. Such local effects are accompanied by high stress levels in the face-plates and in the interfaces between the core and the face-plates. Thus, sandwich structures usually fail in a delamination mode at the face-plate/core interfaces or in the face-plates themselves. These effects are ignored in classical "anti-plane" sandwich plate theories, as summed up in the text books by Allen [1] and Plantema [2].

Whenever external loads have to be introduced into sandwich structures, it is necessary to adopt special means in order to reduce the occurrence of local effects of the type described. A method of achieving this is the application of inserts [3]. An insert is part of a detachable fixation device, which permits the interconnection of adjoining sandwich structures and the mounting of equipment. The system consists of a removable and a fixed element. The removable part is either a screw or another threaded element adapted to a fixed "nut-like" part, the insert. Inserts for sandwich panels exists in many forms, but the only ones which really improves the strength are the types extending all through the thickness of the panels.

The present study deals exclusively with sandwich plates with "through-the-thickness" inserts, and the objective was defined as the development of a mechanical model which includes the complete insert/sandwich panel response assuming general loading conditions.

MODEL DEFINITION AND MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The approach followed in this study is based on the development of a higher-order sandwich plate theory which includes the transverse flexibility of the core material. Thus, the core thickness is allowed to change during deformation of the sandwich panel, and the face-plates are allowed to

deflect differently. This makes the model different from the classical “anti-plane” sandwich plate theories. The model presented in this study has been inspired by the works of Frostig et al. [4], and Frostig [5], [6], which describes the development and application of a higher-order sandwich beam theory with features as described. In the modelling of the insert/sandwich plate system, it is assumed that the interaction between adjacent inserts, as well as the interaction between the inserts and sandwich plate boundaries or other disturbances, can be ignored. Fig. 1 defines the constituent parts, the geometry as well as the possible loading of the adopted model. The sharp separation between the potting and honeycomb materials is a strong idealisation, as the potting/honeycomb intersection is not defined precisely in a geometrical sense in reality.

Figure 1. Definition of model constituent parts, geometry and external loads.

Figure 2. Geometrical definition of sandwich plate element consisting of top face-plate, core material (potting and honeycomb materials) and bottom face-plate.

Due to the limited space available, the details of the derivations cannot be given here, and instead reference is made to Thomsen [7]. However, the principles behind the modelling are described in the following (referring to Figs. 1 and 2 for definition of geometry and displacement components). The core material (potting compound and honeycomb) is described as a special type of isotropic solid, where only the “through-the-thickness” stiffness is accounted for. Setting up the equilibrium conditions, and using the kinematic and constitutive relations yields a set of equations describing the complete core stress and displacement fields in terms of the transverse core coordinate z_c (see Fig. 2):

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{rc}(r, \theta, z_c) &= \tau_{rc}(r, \theta); \quad \tau_{\theta c}(r, \theta, z_c) = \tau_{\theta c}(r, \theta); \\ \sigma_c(r, \theta, z_c) &= \frac{E_c}{c} \{w^1 - w^2\} - \left\{ \tau_{rc,r} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{rc} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{\theta c,\theta} \right\} z_c; \\ w_c(r, \theta, z_c) &= w^1 + \frac{\{w^1 - w^2\}}{c} \left\{ z_c - \frac{c}{2} \right\} - \frac{1}{2E_c} \left\{ \tau_{rc,r} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{rc} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{\theta c,\theta} \right\} \left\{ z_c^2 - \frac{c^2}{4} \right\}; \end{aligned} \quad (1a-1c)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_c(r, \theta, z_c) &= u_{0r}^1 + \frac{w_{,r}^1}{2} \left\{ t_1 - \frac{z_c^2}{c} - z_c + \frac{3c}{4} \right\} + \frac{w_{,r}^2}{2} \left\{ \frac{z_c^2}{c} - z_c + \frac{c}{4} \right\} + \frac{\tau_{r,c}}{G_c} \left\{ z_c - \frac{c}{2} \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2E_c} \left\{ \tau_{r,r,r} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{r,r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \tau_{r,c} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{\theta,c,\theta r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \tau_{\theta,c,\theta} \right\} \left\{ \frac{z_c^3}{3} - \frac{c z_c}{4} + \frac{c^3}{12} \right\}; \\
 v_c(r, \theta, z_c) &= u_{0\theta}^1 + \frac{w_{,\theta}^1}{2r} \left\{ t_1 - \frac{z_c^2}{c} - z_c + \frac{3c}{4} \right\} + \frac{w_{,\theta}^2}{2r} \left\{ \frac{z_c^2}{c} - z_c + \frac{c}{4} \right\} + \frac{\tau_{\theta,c}}{G_c} \left\{ z_c - \frac{c}{2} \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{r2E_c} \left\{ \tau_{r,r,\theta} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{r,\theta} + \frac{1}{r} \tau_{\theta,c,\theta\theta} \right\} \left\{ \frac{z_c^3}{3} - \frac{c^2 z_c}{4} + \frac{c^3}{12} \right\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1d-1e}$$

In Eqns. (1), E_c and G_c are the core elastic constants, σ_c is the core transverse normal stress, $\tau_{r,c}$ and $\tau_{\theta,c}$ are the core shear stresses and differentiation with respect to a spatial coordinate is denoted by a subscript comma. From Eqns. (1) it is seen, that $\tau_{r,c}$ and $\tau_{\theta,c}$ are constant, that σ_c varies linearly, that w_c varies quadratically and finally that u_c and v_c varies cubically over the core thickness. The core material is coupled with the face-plates by requiring continuity of the displacement field across the core/face-plate interfaces. This implies that the following surface tractions and shear stresses are transferred between the core and the face-plates:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Face 1/core-interface: } \sigma_c^{\text{top}} &= \sigma_c(r, \theta, \frac{c}{2}); \quad \tau_{r,c} = \tau_{r,c}(r, \theta); \quad \tau_{\theta,c} = \tau_{\theta,c}(r, \theta); \\
 \text{Face 2/core-interface: } \sigma_c^{\text{bottom}} &= \sigma_c(r, \theta, -\frac{c}{2}); \quad \tau_{r,c} = \tau_{r,c}(r, \theta); \quad \tau_{\theta,c} = \tau_{\theta,c}(r, \theta).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2a-2b}$$

The face-plates are modelled using classical Kirchhoff theory (the face-plates are treated as homogeneous, isotropic and linear elastic, even though the face-plates in many applications are FRP-laminates), and combining the equilibrium, kinematic and constitutive equations for the top and bottom face-plates with the "core equations", Eqns. (1)-(2), yields the set of governing partial differential equations. The order of the set of governing differential equations is 24, and consequently the governing equations can be reduced to 24 first order partial differential equations with 24 unknowns. If the 24 unknowns, henceforth called the fundamental variables, are those quantities which appear in the natural boundary conditions at an edge $r=\text{constant}$, then the boundary value problem can be completely stated in terms of these variables. In the present case, the 24×1 matrix $\{y(r, \theta)\}$ of fundamental variables can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{y(r, \theta)\} &= \{u_{r,0}^1, u_{\theta,0}^1, w^1, \beta_r^1, \beta_\theta^1, N_r^1, N_{r\theta}^1, M_r^1, M_{r\theta}^1, Q_r^1, \\
 &\quad \tau_{r,c}, q_r, \tau_{\theta,c}, q_\theta, u_{r,0}^2, u_{\theta,0}^2, w^2, \beta_r^2, \beta_\theta^2, N_r^2, N_{r\theta}^2, M_r^2, M_{r\theta}^2, Q_r^2\};
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $\beta_r^i, \beta_\theta^i$ are the face midsurface rotations, N_r^i and $N_{r\theta}^i$ are the face in-plane stress resultants, M_r^i and $M_{r\theta}^i$ are the face moment resultants and Q_r^i are the face radial transverse shear stress resultants ($i=1,2$). In Eqn. (3) two new "core-variables" q_r, q_θ have been introduced:

$$q_r(r, \theta) = \tau_{r,r}; \quad q_\theta(r, \theta) = \tau_{\theta,c,r}. \tag{4}$$

Adopting the matrix of fundamental variables $\{y(r, \theta)\}$, the governing equations can be reduced to:

$$\{y\}_{,r} = \Psi(r, \theta, \{y\}, \{y\}_{,\theta}, \{y\}_{,\theta\theta}, \dots); \tag{5}$$

where Ψ denotes 24 linear functions in $\{y\}$ and its derivatives with respect to θ . The dependency of the θ -coordinate is eliminated by Fourier-series expansion of the fundamental variables thus reducing the governing equations to a set of 24 first order ordinary differential equations.

The only thing still needed is the statement of the boundary conditions. The order of the system equations is 24, thus implying that 12 boundary conditions needs to be specified at $r=r_0$ and $r=R$. The statement of the boundary conditions is based on the following assumptions (see Fig. 1):

- $r=r_0$: the insert is considered as an infinitely rigid body to which, the sandwich face-plates and the potting material are “rigidly” connected.
- $r=R$: it is assumed, that the face-plates and the honeycomb core material are simply supported.

The set of governing equations (Eqn. (5)) together with the statement of the boundary conditions, constitutes a boundary value problem, which is solved using the “multi-segment method” of integration. Without going into details, the method is based on a transformation of the original boundary value problem into a series of initial value problems. The insert/sandwich plate is divided into a finite number of segments, and the solution within each segment is accomplished by direct integration (simultaneous integration of $24 \times 24 = 576$ first order differential equations). Continuity of the solution vectors across the separation points between the segments, as well as fulfilment of the boundary conditions, is ensured by formulating and solving a set of linear algebraic equations. For detailed information about the “multi-segment method” of integration, reference is made to [8], [9]. The implementation of the direct integration scheme, was carried out using a UNIX-version of the mathematical software-package MATLAB[®] (version 4.1), installed on HP9000/700 workstation. The direct integration was carried out using a MATLAB[®]-routine based on an “adaptive step-size” 4th and 5th order Runge-Kutta-Fehlberg method.

IMPLICATIONS/LIMITATIONS OF THEORY

As already mentioned, the face-plates are assumed to behave as homogeneous, isotropic and linear elastic materials. Clearly, this assumption is not generally justified, as face-plates made as orthotropic FRP-laminates are frequently used. However, the laminate lay-ups used in zones where inserts are mounted are usually quasi-isotropic (or nearly so), thus making at least the “in-plane” face-plate properties very close to being isotropic. For the cases where slightly orthotropic face-plates are used, the present formulation will provide sufficiently accurate results if the elastic coefficients of the face-plates E_i , ν_i^2 ($i=1,2$) are replaced by “average”-quantities defined by $(E_{xi}$

$E_{yi})^{1/2}$ and $(\nu_{xyi} \nu_{yxi})$ ($i=1,2$), respectively (subscripts x and y : principal material directions). For the rare cases where strongly orthotropic face-laminates are used, the model suggested is not applicable. It is, however, possible to include orthotropic face-plate properties in the formulation.

In the suggested theory, the honeycomb core material is modelled as being a homogeneous, isotropic and linear elastic material which supplies a continuous support for the face-plates. This is in conflict with the physical problem on two points. Firstly, the hexagonal cell structure of honeycombs results in orthotropic in-plane properties. Orthotropic core properties can in principle be included in the analysis, but this has not been carried out as this would complicate the formulation. Secondly, the discrete cellular nature of honeycomb materials has been excluded from the analysis, as the honeycomb properties are effectively treated as “smeared out” over the honeycomb cell areas. Thus, the stresses obtained for the honeycomb material should be considered as “averaged” over the core cell areas. Consequently, the actual load transfer mechanisms in the cell walls of the honeycomb core are not reflected by the “average” core stresses obtained. The stresses obtained, however, complies well with the material data supplied by the manufacturers, as they supply “smeared” or overall stiffness and strength properties.

As mentioned earlier, the assumption of a sharp separation between the potting and the honeycomb represents an idealisation. In reality, the potting/honeycomb intersection is irregular, as it is created when the potting flows into those of the honeycomb cells which have been left open during machining. This problem can only be surmounted by adopting a model which accounts for the discrete nature of the cellular honeycomb materials (i.e. by detailed finite element modelling). Pertaining to comparison of the suggested higher-order sandwich plate theory with classical “anti-plane” theories [1]-[2], the following comparative features should be highlighted:

- The suggested higher-order theory supplies information about the individual displacements of the face-plates, as well as of each point in the core material (non-linear displacements over the core thickness).
- As opposed to this, classical theories assume the core thickness to be constant. Consequently, the in-plane face-plate and core displacements varies linearly over the thickness.

- Both types of theories assumes that the core shear stresses are constant over the core thickness, and there is very little difference between the predicted values. However, the higher-order sandwich plate theory accounts for the existence of transverse normal stresses in the core material, which plays an important role in the onset and development of failure.

EXAMPLE

To give an impression of the mechanical response of sandwich plates with "through-the-thickness" inserts, an example will be given. The example chosen is a symmetric sandwich plate with a central insert subjected to an out-of-plane force Q (axisymmetric case; see Fig. 1). The geometry, material and load data are (see Fig. 1 for reference):

- Geometry:* $r_0=10\text{ mm}$; $r_p=30\text{ mm}$; $R=150\text{ mm}$; $c=10\text{ mm}$; $t_1=t_2=1\text{ mm}$.
Face 1: Quasi-isotropic FRP-laminate with properties: $E_1=40\text{ GPa}$; $\nu_1=0.3$.
Face 2: As face 1 (symmetric sandwich panel), i.e. $E_2=E_1$; $\nu_2=\nu_1$;
Potting: Bulk epoxy polymer with material properties: $E_p=2.5\text{ GPa}$; $G_p=0.93\text{ GPa}$.
Honeycomb: HEXCEL Al-honeycomb 3/16"-5056-0.0007" with properties: $E_h=310\text{ MPa}$ (through-the-thickness direction); $G_h=(G_L+G_W)/2=138\text{ MPa}$.
Load: $Q=-1\text{ kN}$ (out-of-plane load).

For examples involving other load cases (T , N and M , see Fig. 1), reference is made to [7]. Fig. 3 shows, the out-of-plane deflections of the face-plates (w^1 , w^2), and the core midsurface ($w_c(z_c=0)$). It is noticed that $r \leq r_p = 30\text{ mm}$ corresponds to the potting region, whereas $r > 30\text{ mm}$ corresponds to the honeycomb region. It is seen that the out-of-plane deflections of the two face-plates and the core material midsurface ($z_c=0$) are almost identical. As expected due to the symmetry of the sandwich plate, the out-of-plane displacements of the two face-plates w^1 , w^2 are identical. The midsurface out-of-plane displacement of the core material $w_c(z_c=0)$, however, is slightly different from $w^1=w^2$ even though, the difference is so small that it is hardly recognisable. It is observed that the "slopes" changes distinctly at $r=r_p=30\text{ mm}$, i.e. at the potting/honeycomb intersection, where the core-stiffness changes from $E_c=E_p=2.5\text{ GPa}$ to $E_c=E_h=0.31\text{ GPa}$.

Figure 3. Out-of-plane displacements w^1 , w^2 , $w_c(z_c=0)$ of sandwich plate with "through-the-thickness" insert subjected to out-of-plane force $Q=-1\text{ kN}$.

Fig. 4 shows the radial distribution of core stresses. The values of σ_c are given at the interface between face-plate 1 and the core (σ_c^{top}) and at the interface between face-plate 2 and the core (σ_c^{bottom}). Fig. 4 also shows the distribution of the core shear stress component τ_{rz} . It is observed that the presence of transverse normal stresses is a local phenomenon, as significant σ_c

stresses are only present close to $r=r_0=10\text{ mm}$ (i.e. close to the insert) and close to $r=r_p=30\text{ mm}$ (i.e. close to the potting/honeycomb intersection). It is seen that σ_c^{top} raises from zero (at $r=r_0$) and attains a compressive peak close to $r=r_0$. After this peak value, σ_c^{top} drops to zero very quickly, but raises to another compressive peak value as r approaches $r=r_p=30\text{ mm}$. At $r=r_p$ σ_c^{top} drops to zero again, but raises abruptly to a tensile peak value, 1-2 mm after $r=r_p$. The decay of σ_c^{top} is complete about one sandwich plate thickness from $r=r_p$. With respect to σ_c^{bottom} , the exact same pattern is observed (symmetric sandwich plate) except that the sign of σ_c^{bottom} is opposite to that of σ_c^{top} .

Considering the shear stress distribution in the core material, the overall tendency is that τ_{rz} decreases with increasing r -values, except over a short range close to $r=r_0$ where τ_{rz} increases slightly. The overall tendency of decreasing τ_{rz} -values with increasing r is a consequence of the fact, that the "total" transverse shear stress resultant $Q_r^{total}=Q_r^I+Q_r^2+c \tau_{rz}$ is inversely proportional to r ($Q=2\pi r Q_r^{total}$), and that the main part of Q is carried by the core material (i.e. by τ_{rz}). However, due to the restrictive boundary conditions imposed at $r=r_0$ the face-plates carries a comparatively large part of the out-of-plane load Q for r -values close to $r=r_0$. After the peak value of τ_{rz} has been encountered, τ_{rz} decreases as predicted by classical sandwich theories [1]-[2].

Figure 4. Core stress components τ_{rz} , σ_c^{top} , σ_c^{bottom} in sandwich plate with "through-the-thickness" insert subjected to out-of-plane force $Q=-1\text{ kN}$.

An important conclusion, pertaining to the results presented, is that the use of classical "anti-plane" sandwich plate theory would not have revealed the complicated stress transfer mechanisms which have been demonstrated in the core material. This, of course, is due to the fact that the classical theories deals with the "overall" sandwich plate response rather than describing the individual mechanical responses of the face-plates and the core.

No further results will be given here, and reference is made to [7] for details about the stress transfer in the face-plates.

PARAMETRIC EFFECTS

The results presented so far have demonstrated a few features of the response of sandwich plates with "through-the-thickness" inserts subjected to out-of-plane loading, but in order to gain a more thorough understanding, it is necessary to conduct a parametric study. However, due to the limited space available, only a few parametric results can be included in this paper, and reference is made

to [7] for the results of a more elaborate study. The parametric results included in this paper have been derived by variation from the following symmetric sandwich plate configuration:

- Geometry: $r_0=10\text{ mm}$; $r_p=30\text{ mm}$; $R=150\text{ mm}$; $c=10\text{ mm}$; $t_1=t_2=1\text{ mm}$.
 Face 1: Quasi-isotropic FRP-laminate with properties: $E_1=40\text{ GPa}$; $\nu_1=0.3$.
 Face 2: As face 1 (symmetric sandwich panel), i.e. $E_2=E_1$; $\nu_2=\nu_1$.
 Honeycomb: HEXCEL Al-honeycomb 1/8"-5056-0.0007" with properties: $E_h=668\text{ MPa}$ (through-the-thickness direction); $G_h=(G_L+G_W)/2=224\text{ MPa}$.
 Load: $Q=-1\text{ kN}$ (out-of-plane load).

The results to be shown will demonstrate the effect of changing the elastic modulus of the potting compound (E_p) with fixed honeycomb properties, fixed face-plate properties, fixed geometry and fixed out-of-plane load ($Q=-1\text{ kN}$).

Fig. 5 shows the peak core stress components as functions of E_p/E_h . Considering Fig. 5, there might be some confusion with respect to the proper interpretation of the results presented for $E_p/E_h=1$. Evidently, $E_p/E_h=1$ corresponds to a situation where the elastic properties in the potting and the honeycomb regions are identical. As the honeycomb properties have been kept constant in the parametric variations, it is clear that $E_p/E_h=1$ means that no potting is present. With this made clear, the meaning of having separate curves for $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{potting})\}_{peak}=-\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{potting})\}_{peak}$ and $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}=-\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}$ is somewhat obscured. The correct interpretation is, that only one transverse normal stress peak is present on each surface of the core material for $E_p/E_h=1$ (see Fig. 4 for comparison), as there is no abrupt change of core properties. Thus, " $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}=-\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}=0$ " and " $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{potting})\}_{peak}=\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{potting})\}_{peak}\neq 0$ " for $E_p/E_h=1$, as required by the physical nature of the problem.

Figure 5. Peak values of σ_c^{top} , σ_c^{bottom} and τ_{rz} vs. E_p/E_h ($E_h=668\text{ MPa}=\text{fixed}$) for symmetric sandwich plate configurations (fixed face-plate properties). External load $Q=-1\text{ kN}$.

With respect to $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{potting})\}_{peak}=-\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{potting})\}_{peak}$, it is observed that they are not severely influenced by variation of the parameter E_p/E_h , whereas $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}=-\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}$ varies significantly when the value of E_p/E_h is altered. Thus, it is seen that $\{\sigma_c^{top}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}=-\{\sigma_c^{bottom}(\text{honeycomb})\}_{peak}$ changes sign when the E_p/E_h -values crosses $E_p/E_h=1$. With respect to the peak core shear stresses, $\{\tau_{rz}\}_{peak}$, it is observed that they increase steadily (but slowly) when E_p/E_h is increased.

DESIGN GUIDELINES

Based on the results given in this paper, together with the results presented in [7], a set of guidelines for the design of sandwich plates with "through-the-thickness" inserts have been formulated:

- If possible, the radial extension of the potting compound (denoted by r_p-r_0 , see Fig. 1) should at least be one core thickness. This choice of r_p-r_0 will ensure that maximum relief of the face-plate bending and shear stress concentrations is achieved, while, at the same time, the full shear stress transfer capability of the potting compound is utilised.
- If possible, the ratio of the potting stiffness to the honeycomb stiffness, E_p/E_h , should be chosen such that $E_p/E_h \approx 3-4$. This will ensure a good compromise between the peak stress level in the face-plates and in the potting and honeycomb materials.
- It is generally recommended to avoid external bending moment loading (M load case). This can be achieved by load application through groups of "through-the-thickness" inserts, thus "converting" the bending moment loading to out-of-plane loads on the inserts.
- As significant stress concentrations in the potting material, as well as in the adhesive bond-lines between the honeycomb core and face-plate materials, are unavoidable, the potting and adhesive materials should possess long elongation to failure capability (good ductility).

CONCLUSIONS

A higher-order sandwich plate theory has been developed and adapted for the analysis of sandwich panels with "through-the-thickness" inserts. The development of the mathematical model has been based on the simplifying assumptions, that the face-plates as well as the potting and honeycomb materials behaves as linear elastic, homogeneous and isotropic materials. The higher-order sandwich plate theory (of 24'th order) includes the following features: separate descriptions of the structural responses of each of the face-plates as well as of the core material, specification of different "potting" and "honeycomb" properties and finally general specification of the external loads. The problem solution for specific insert/sandwich plate configurations, has been accomplished by transforming the resulting boundary value problem into a series of interconnected initial value problems, which has been solved using the "multi-segment method" of integration.

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